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Press Release

Accelerating Data Solutions to save LIVES from COVID-19

Today the consortium of COVID-X announces the launch of the [1st Open Call](#) framed in a 2-year initiative that will invest **4 million €** to fast-track to market **30+ European data technology solutions** defeating COVID-19 Challenges, facilitating an innovative stack of AI-driven tools.

COVID-19 pandemic is hitting with force. Europe has passed the threshold of **250,000 deaths** since February 2020. **COVID-X** takes the battle against coronavirus to a new level by bridging the gap between the European digital sector and the healthcare system. The program will **unlock the full capacity of Artificial Intelligence and Data to fight COVID-19**, validating, and scaling up breakthroughs to save lives.

COVID-X will fund **EU Companies** and **Healthcare Providers** to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up. The funding is invested in products with TRL 7+ and [or in the process of] CE marking, covering two profiles: **single players** (EU Tech SMEs / Start-Ups) validating their solutions at one of COVID-X clinical partners; or **multiplayers** (Tech Provider working with a Healthcare provider that will validate the solution). The selected projects will join an **Acceleration Program to boost their quick market uptake**. This will include technical support, ethical validation, and business coaching.

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In addition, participants will have access to the **COVID-X Sandbox**, a one-stop platform to exploit COVID-19 data sources, incorporating general information on data silos, as well as the integration, visualization, and exploratory analysis for easy understanding.

The 1st Open Call Application is **now open** and the deadline will be on **the 27th January 2021**.

COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from 7 different countries:

CIVITTA

HUMANITAS
RESEARCH HOSPITAL

For more information

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